

DEMOGRAPHIC AND PERSONALITY CORRELATES OF PRINCIPALS' PERFORMANCE IN INSTRUCTIONAL SUPERVISION IN THE MANAGEMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN SOUTH-SOUTH, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study examined the relationship between demographic and personality variables and principal performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria. The correlational survey design was adopted for the study. Four research questions and one hypothesis guided the study. The population of the study comprised 1,356 principals of public secondary schools. The sample for the study consisted of 310 principals obtained using Taro Yamen's formula, while 1860 teachers rated their principals. Proportionate stratified random sampling was used to select the number of principals per state while disproportionate stratified random sampling was used to select the number of principals and teachers per senatorial zone for fair representation. Three instruments namely: principals' motivational factors questionnaire (PMFQ), principals' leadership style questionnaire (PLSQ), and principals' instructional supervision performance scale (PISPS) were used for data collection. These instruments were face validated by three experts and their overall internal consistency reliability coefficient indices obtained through the Cronbach alpha method were 0.97 for PMFQ, 0.60 for PLSQ, and 0.67 for PISPS. Means, standard deviations, and correlation coefficient were used to answer the four research questions while multiple regressions and associated t-tests were used to test the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed among others that most principals were males, married, and have served as principals and vice-principals for not more than 11 years. Principals in South-South, Nigeria exhibited open leadership styles. The factors that motivated principals in the performance of their duties were the nature of work, recognition, responsibility, achievement, and prospects for advancement. Principals' performance was high in instructional supervision. Leadership styles and location had substantial correlation coefficients with principals' performance instructional supervision. Demographic and personality factors had a joint significant relationship ($P < 0.05$) with principals' performance in instructional supervision. These variables predicted 16.3% of the variance in instructional supervision. Leadership style and location predicted the performance of principals in instructional supervision. Based on these findings, it was recommended in the appointment of principals, leadership behaviour and school location should be considered since these variables had a significant relationship with principals' performance in instructional supervision. Besides, training and re-training programmes should be given to principals to help them adopt more open leadership styles for effectiveness.

Keywords:

*Demographics,
management,
Secondary school,
Principals.*

Introduction

The National Policy of Education described Secondary education as a six-year form of education that children receive after primary school and before tertiary education. The aim is to prepare individuals for useful living within society and for higher education. The Principal is the administrative head of the Secondary School. The Principal is responsible for the management of

secondary schools in different tasks such as instructional supervision. Supervision of instruction is the process of ensuring that effective teaching and learning takes place in the school system. Instructional supervision according to Mgbodile (2004) involves the task of ensuring that organized teaching and learning is effective in the school. The effective performance of principals in instructional supervision determines to a large extent the growth and development of secondary schools in Nigeria. Effective supervision of instruction ensures that teachers teach what they are supposed to teach and the students learn what they are supposed to learn. The principal must see that meaningful learning takes place in all classes and those teachers are teaching what they are supposed to teach and are undertaking the teaching in a manner that the students understand and enjoy their lessons. The essence of instructional supervision is to assist teachers with ideas and suggestions that will improve their instructional delivery, as well as identify their needs and problems. Haruna (2008) noted that instructional supervision is the first and the most important responsibility of a school principal. No wonder Carter (2008) explained that the cardinal index of the performance evaluation of the school administrator rests on the leadership ability in instructional supervision. Similarly, Chika and Ebeke (2007) observed that among many factors that influence learning and achievement in secondary schools, principals' instructional management seem to be the most critical intervening factor.

The role of instructional supervision in educational management and control may be viewed as that of monitoring different aspects of the school system in terms of resource utilization and relating them to the level of educational goal achievement. This role according to Eferakeya cited in Igwe (2003) involves establishing and clarifying role relationships; developing the curriculum - setting a goal, planning learning experiences, allocating resources; supervision of programmes including procurement and allocation of instructional materials and equipment; evaluation of programmes – checking of notes of lesson, scheme of work, diaries, registers and financial records; provision and submission of all school records on demand to the inspectors for cross-checking.

The development of the curriculum is an aspect where the principal is expected to play a leading role in instructional development. Keoreng (2004) stated that the principal should play this role as a team leader by way of guiding teachers either directly or in conjunction with the heads of department in terms of helping to identify relevant goals to the community, planning and selecting relevant learning experiences, helping to implement programmes improvement and evaluating changes.

Evaluation as principals' role in instructional supervision entails judging the extent to which school objectives have been achieved. According to Mgbodile (2004), evaluation of teachers is needed in the school to measure the quality of services rendered by the teachers. Mgbodile noted that the school head should undertake periodic supervision of the classes to ensure that meaningful teaching and learning are taking place. Enyi (2012) noted that principals should also inspect teacher's notes of lessons beforehand to ensure that they were well written and set in line with the scheme of work to enhance effective teaching. The Principal will also have to observe the teacher in class during class delivery to get an insight into the teacher's mastery of the content, method of lesson delivery, the use of instructional media, classroom control, technique of asking questions and manner of involving students in active learning as well as his evaluation techniques to ensure that student understands and enjoy their lessons (Agbo, 2013). Through evaluation, the principal and teachers can identify areas where special attention should be paid to a particular subject for the interest of the learner. On the other hand, students' evaluation is also necessary as a measure of their progress. By evaluating the students orally, written or practical examination, the extent to which they understand the curriculum content is ascertained. Through evaluation of students, the principal will be able to determine the capability of his teachers and determine whether the pupils are learning and whether they are making progress individually and

collectively. Oyewale and Alonge (2013) noted that the principal as the school administrator should perform the within-school supervisory role in instructional improvement and the evaluation of education by assisting teachers to determine the right methods, teaching facilities, physical setting, and classroom attributes that are likely to promote effective learning. Principals' performance in instructional supervision is how well or frequently the principal carries out his roles in the supervision of instruction.

The objectives of instructional supervision have been stressed. Lamude & Torres (2000) noted that instructional supervision enhances quality control through regular and continuous monitoring of instructional services, and identifying the needs and problems of teachers. Contributing on the subject, Okwor (2001) emphasized that in a situation where the principal devotes little or no time to instructional responsibilities, the quality of education been offered to the students cannot be effectively and adequately ascertained and guaranteed.

It has been noted from the available evidence that the methods of selection of secondary school principals in Nigeria, which does not consider demographic and personality variables are unsatisfactory and gives room for concern (Nwosu, 2009). The consequence of this anomaly is that most of the school principals grope around and often use trial and error methods in the day-to-day school administration. This gives rise to low morale and poor work attitude that affect their performance in task areas such as instructional supervision. There are theoretical and empirical connections among these demographic and personality variables and performance. For instance, there is the general proposition that younger principals exhibit better management capabilities than the old principals since individuals tend to disengage from active work with age. This was buttressed by Oredien (2004) that showed a positive relationship between principals' productivity and age. However, in a study, Domina (2005) found that there was no significant relationship between principals' age and administrative performance. Also, while some research studies showed evidence of male superiority over females in task performance (Uko, 2002), some others reported that females perform better in school administration (Daresh & Male, 2000). Sturman (2000) noted that experience has some level of influence on principals' job performance. The relationship may differ depending on the task areas of the management of secondary schools. Similarly, professional qualification has some research evidence in support of its potential in improving principals' job performance (Nwangwu, 2006), Ogbaji and Oti (2006) posited that the professional qualification of principals has no impact on their job performance. Due to these inconsistencies, it has become necessary to examine the extent to which these variables relate to the performance of principals in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools in South-South Nigeria. It is against this background that the researcher focused to find out the relationships between these variables and principals' performance in instructional supervision.

Statement of the Problem

The success of any educational system depends largely on the quality of learning instruction given to the learner. The essence of instructional supervision seems not to be achieved in most schools in South-South, Nigeria hence the perceived decrepitude in the standard of education. Today, moral decadence and other social vices have become very prevalent in the school system. All these shortcomings have been blamed on the school principals. Parents expect the school to provide solutions to all these problems as the school is considered to be an agent of change within the Nigerian society, and of course all over the world. Principals' performance in instructional supervision the management of secondary schools has remained questionable in South-South, Nigeria. This is due to the deplorable state of the schools evidenced in students' poor performance in the public examination which has led to a public outcry. It has been observed that demographic factors like educational qualification, experience, age, gender, specialization, marital status and personality factors such as leadership style and motivation may have

relationships with principals' performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria. The extent to which these variables relate with principals' performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria has not been determined. The problem of the study is: To what extent do demographic (age, gender, qualification, experience, marital status) and personality (leadership styles, motivation) variables relate with or predict principals' performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria?

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the relationships between demographic and personality factors, and the performance of principals in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain the:

1. Demographic and personality profile of principals,
2. Performance of principals in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools,
3. Demographic and personality correlates of principals performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools, and;
4. Demographic and personality factors that predict principals' performance instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools.

Research questions

The following research questions are posed to guide the study.

1. What is the demographic (age, gender, educational qualification, working experience and marital status) profile of principals of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria?
2. What is the personality (leadership styles and motivation) profile of principals of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria?
3. What are the principals' mean performance scores in instructional supervision in the management in the management of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria?
4. What are the correlation coefficients between demographic and personality variables and principals' performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis will be tested at a 0.05 level of probability.

1. Demographic and personality variables do not significantly relate with principals' performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted a correlational survey design. The population of the study comprised 1,356 principals of public secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria. The sample for the study consisted of 310 principals obtained using Taro Yamen's formula. To arrive at the sample size of 310 principals, a proportionate stratified random sampling technique using the same Taro Yamen's formula was used to select the required number of principals per senatorial zone and then the states for fair representation. Three instruments namely: principals' motivational factors questionnaire (PMFQ), principals' leadership style questionnaire (PLSQ), and principals' instructional supervision performance scale (PISPS) were used for data collection. These instruments were face validated by three experts and the overall internal consistency reliability co-efficient indices of the instruments obtained through the Cronbach alpha method were 0.97 for PMFQ, 0.60 for PLSQ, and 0.67 for PISPS. Data were collected through the direct delivery method by the researcher and seven research assistants. Means, standard deviations, and

correlation coefficient were used to answer the four research questions while multiple regressions and associated t-tests were used to test the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The results were presented in line with the research question and null hypothesis that guided the study as showed in the tables below:

Research Question One: What is the demographic (age, gender, educational qualification, working experience and marital status) profile of principals of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria?

Data for providing answers to the above research questions are presented in tables 1-6.

Table 1: Frequencies and percentage of principals' age in South-South, Nigeria.

Category (years)	Frequencies	Percentage
36-40	2	0.60
41-45	7	2.20
46-50	41	13.20
51-55	184	59.30
56-60	76	24.60
Total	310	100.00

Table 1 revealed that 184 (59.3%) principals were within the age bracket of 51-55 years, 76(24.6%) were within the age bracket of 56-60 years, 41(13.2%) were within the age bracket of 46-50 years, 7(2.2%) were within the age bracket of 41-45 years, while 2 (.6%) were within the age bracket of 36-40 years. A summary of this table revealed that most principals in South-South, Nigeria were within the age bracket of 51-55 years.

Table 2: Frequencies and percentage of principals' gender in secondary schools in South-South Nigeria.

Category	Frequencies	Percentage
Male	201	64.80
Female	109	35.20
Total	310	100.00

Table 2 revealed that 201 principals (64.8%) were males while 109(35.2%) were females. Most principals in South-South, Nigeria were Males.

Table 3: Frequencies and percentage of principals' years of working experience in South-South Nigeria.

Category	Frequencies		Percentage	
	Principal	VP	Principal (%)	VP (%)
< 1	-	11	-	3.50
1-5	74	106	23.00	34.20
6-10	116	157	37.40	50.60
11-15	92	27	29.70	7.40
16-20	18	4	5.90	1.20
21-25	4	2	1.20	0.60
26-30	3	7	0.90	2.30
31-35	3	-	0.90	-
Total	310	310	100.00	100.00

Table 3 showed that 116 (37.4%) principals have served for a period of 6-10 years; 92(29.7%) principals have served for 11-15 years; 74(23.8%) principals have served for 1-5 years; 18(5.9%) principals have served for 16-20 years; 4(1.2%) principals who have served for 21-25 years; and 3(0.9%) principals have served for 26-30 and 31-35 years respectively. In addition, the table showed that before becoming principals, 157 (50.7%) of them have been Vice principals for 6-10 years; 106(34.2%) have served as Vice principals for 1-5 years; 27(7.4%) have been Vice principals for 11-15 years, 7(2.3%) have been Vice Principals for 20-30 years, 4(1.2%) have served as Vice Principals for 16-20 years; 2(0.6%) of them have served for 21-25 years as Vice Principals, and 11(3.5%) of them have served as Vice principals for less than a year before being principal. In summary, this table showed that most principals 282 (90.2%) in South-South Nigeria have a working experience of fewer than 15 years with only 3 who have served for 31-35 years. The majority of the 274 (88.3%) were vice Principals for less than 11 years before becoming Principals.

Table 4: Frequencies and percentage of principals' educational qualifications in South-South Nigeria.

Category	Frequencies	Percentage
PhD	3	
M.Sc/ M.A/M.Ed	93	1
B.Sc/B.A/B.Ed/B.Sc(Ed)	213	30
Dip/NCE	1	68.70
Total	310	0.30
		100.00

Table 4 showed that only 3(1%) of the principals had a PhD; 93(30%) had a second degree such as M.Sc/M.A/M.Ed; 213(68.7%) have a first degree like B.Sc/B.A/B.Ed/B.Sc(Ed.); and only 1(3%) principal had Diploma or NCE. Most of the principals in South-South, Nigeria had the first degree.

Table 5: Frequencies and percentage of principals' area of speciality in secondary schools in South-South Nigeria.

Category	Frequencies	Percentage
Educational Administration /Planning	32	10.30%
Other Aspects of Education	258	83.20%
No Education Qualification	20	6.50%
Total	310	100.00%

Table 5 showed that 32(10.3%) principals specialized in educational administration and planning; 258(83.2%) specialized in other aspects of education, while 20(6.5%) specialized in other areas without any educational qualification. This table revealed that most principals in South-South, Nigeria had a qualification in education and that 6.5% of them were not professionally qualified to be principals.

Table 6: Frequencies and percentage of principals' marital status in South-South, Nigeria.

Category	Frequencies	Percentage
Married	302	97.40%
Single	4	1.30%
Divorce	3	1%
Separated	1	0.30%
Total	310	100.00%

Table 6 showed that 302(97.4%) principals were married; 4(1.3%) were single; 3(1%) were divorced, while only 1(.3%) was separated. This table showed that most principals in South-South, Nigeria were married.

Research Question 2

What is the personality (leadership styles and motivation) profile of principals of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria?

The leadership behaviour of secondary schools principals in South-South Nigeria is presented in table 7.

Table 7: Means ratings of principals' leadership behaviours in the management of Secondary Schools in South-South Nigeria.

S/N	Questionnaire items	X	SD	DEC
1	communicates openly to staff about school activities	3.44	.68	A
2	encourages self-expression, creativity and interaction in the school	3.31	.68	A
3	showed a feeling of concern and respect for staff	3.26	.74	A
4	delegates duties to staff	3.37	.66	A
5	involve teachers in decision making	3.00	.82	A
*6	nags at teachers openly	3.00	1.33	A
7	makes appeal rather than commands staff	3.00	.77	A
*8	imposes tasks and duties on teachers	2.87	.83	A
9	concedes to a high level of staff independence in school activities	2.48	.81	D
*10	wants things done in his/her way	2.77	.95	A
11	is concerned about staff feelings	3.03	.79	A
12	apportions blames to staff when things go wrong	2.47	.94	D
*13	is resistant to change	2.86	.89	A
*14	is indifferent about activities in the school	2.95	.89	A
15	showed concern for school goals and staff welfare	3.27	.38	A
	Grand	3.01	.38	A

*Negative items scored in reverse order - A=Agree, D=Disagree, DEC= Decision

Table 7 showed that items 1-8, 10, 11 and 13 – 15 had high means scores above the bench mark of 2.50. Their mean scores were 3.26, 3.37, 3.00, 3.00, 3.00, 3.00, 2.87, 2.77, 3.03, 2.86, 2.95 and 3.27, while their respective standard deviations were .74, .66, .82, 1.33, .77, .83, .81, .95, .79, .94, .89 and .38. Items 9 and 12 had low means scores of 2.48 and 2.47 with standard deviations of .81 and .94 respectively. The grand mean score and standard deviation were 3.01 and .38 respectively.

Based on the data, the respondents shared the view that principals communicate openly to staff about school activities, encourages self-expression, creativity and interaction in the schools, showed a feeling of concern and respect for staff, and delegate's duties to staff. The principals' also involve teachers in decision making, do not nag at teachers openly, makes appeal rather than commands staff, and do not impose task and duties on teachers. It was also revealed that the principals' are concerned about staff feelings, and do not want things done their way and apportion blames to staff when things go wrong. It was revealed that principals are not indifferent about activities in the school, as they show concern for school goals and staff welfare. The grand mean score and standard deviation indicated openness and democratic tendencies of principals in the management of secondary in South-South, Nigeria.

The motivation profile of secondary schools principals' in South-South Nigeria was presented in tables 8-12.

Table 8: Means ratings on ‘nature of work itself’ as Motivating factor for Principals’ performance in the management of Secondary Schools in South-South Nigeria.

S/N	Questionnaire items (work itself)	\bar{X}	SD	DEC
As a School principal,				
1	The work I am doing is meaningful	3.81	.40	SA
2	The work I am doing is interesting	3.57	.51	SA
3	The job I am doing requires my initiatives	3.59	.50	SA
4	My job is not threatened	2.77	.94	A
5	I derive pleasure in my job	3.48	.56	A
6	The job I am doing is challenging	3.42	.57	A
Cluster		3.44	.31	A

SA= Strongly Agreed, A=Agree, DEC= Decision

Table 8 showed that all the items from 1 to 6 had high mean scores of 3.81, 3.57, 3.59, 2.77, 3.48, 3.42, and 3.44 with standard deviations of .40, .51, .50, .94, .56, and .57 respectively. The cluster mean and standard deviation were 3.44 and .31 respectively. The table revealed that all the items under the nature of work motivated principals in their job. It was revealed that the work of the principal is meaningful, interesting, and requires their initiatives. Besides, it was revealed that the principals' job was not threatened though challenging and that they derive pleasure in it. The cluster mean and standard deviation indicated that the nature of work itself is seen as a motivating factor for principals' performance in the management of secondary education in South-South Nigeria.

Table 9: Means ratings on ‘recognition’ as a motivating factor for Principals’ performance in the management of Secondary Schools in South-South Nigeria

S/N	Questionnaire items (recognition)	\bar{X}	SD	DEC
As a School principal,				
7	My opinion is highly valued at PTA meetings	3.25	.58	A
8	There is a meaningful recognition of accomplished tasks by the PTA and Schools Board	2.97	.71	A
9	I am always commended by PTA and Schools Board when I do well	2.84	.75	A
10	My views are sought for in decision making	2.73	.82	A
11	I am often used as a point of reference for the successful accomplishment of the task	2.72	.83	A
Cluster		2.90	.51	A

A=Agree, DEC= Decision

Table 9 revealed that items 7 to 11 had high mean scores of 3.25, 2.97, 2.84, 2.73, and 2.72, with standard deviations of .58, .71, .75, .82, and .83 respectively. The cluster mean and standard deviation were 2.90 and .51 respectively. The table showed that all the items under-recognition was seen as motivators. It was revealed that principals' opinions were highly valued at PTA meets, there was meaningful recognition of accomplished tasks of the principal by PTA and Schools Board. Besides, the principals were always commended by PTA and Schools Board when they do well and their views were sought for in decision making. Finally, the principals were often used as a point of reference for the successful accomplishment of the task. The cluster mean and standard deviation indicated that recognition was seen as a motivation factor for principals' performance in the management of secondary education in South-South Nigeria.

Table 10: Means ratings on 'responsibility as a motivating factor for Principals' performance in the management of Secondary Schools in South-South Nigeria

S/N	Questionnaire items (responsibility)	\bar{X}	SA	DEC
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As a School principal,				
12	I am not redundant on the job	3.55	.54	SA
13	I preside over Staff meetings	3.73	.47	SA
14	I participate in the supervision of instruction in my school.	3.57	.52	SA
15	I supervise various sections of the school	3.57	.53	SA
16	I nominate my staff to participate in available conferences/workshops	3.35	.59	A
17	I am the custodian of all important records of my school	3.47	.58	A
18	I am an officer of the PTA	3.43	.65	A
Cluster		3.52	.32	SA

SA= Strongly Agreed, A=Agree, DEC= Decision

Table 10 showed all the items from 12 to 18 had high mean scores of 3.55, 3.73, 3.57, 3.57, 3.35, 3.47, and 3.43 with standard deviations of .54, .47, .52, .53, .59, .58, and .65 respectively. The cluster mean and standard deviation were 3.52 and .32 respectively. The table showed that all the items under responsibility are motivating factors. The principals were not redundant in office, they presided over staff meetings, and participate in the supervision of instruction in the school. They also supervised various sections of the school and nominate staff to participate in available conferences/workshops. They are officers of the Parent-Teacher Association and custodians of all important records of the school. The cluster mean and standard deviation indicated that 'responsibility' was strongly seen as a motivating factor for principals' performance in the management of secondary education in South-South, Nigeria.

Table 11: Means ratings on 'achievement' as Motivational factor for Principals' performance in the management of Secondary Schools in South-South Nigeria

S/N	Questionnaire items (achievement)	\bar{X}	SD	DEC
As a School principal,				
19	My students are doing well	3.27	.50	A
20	My staff are making some socio-economic progress	3.17	.50	A
21	There is improvement in infrastructure in my school	2.55	.96	A
22	School-Community relationship is cordial	3.14	.60	A
Cluster		3.03	.42	A

A=Agree, DEC= Decision

The table revealed that items 19 to 22 had high mean scores of 3.27, 3.17, 2.55, and 3.14, with standard deviations of .50, .50, .96, and .60, respectively. The cluster mean and standard deviation were 3.03 and .42 respectively. Therefore, all the items underachievement was seen as motivators. In the principals' opinion, students were doing well, staff was making some socio-economic progress, there was an improvement in infrastructure in the schools, and the School-Community relationship was cordial. The cluster mean and standard deviation indicated that 'achievement' was a motivating factor for principals' performance in the management of secondary education in South-South Nigeria.

Table 12: Means ratings on 'advancement' as a Motivating factor for Principals' performance in the management of Secondary Schools in South-South Nigeria

S/N	Questionnaire items (advancement)	\bar{X}	SD	DEC
As a School principal,				
23	I have acquired further education and training since becoming principal	2.62	.94	A
24	I have acquired management experience on the job	3.45	2.32	A
25	There is support for professional growth	2.42	.88	D
26	There is the possibility of self-actualization	3.21	.52	A
27	There is an opportunity for promotion	3.26	.56	A

Cluster	2.99	.62	A
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A=Agree, D=Disagree, DEC= Decision

Table 12 showed all the items from 23 to 27 except item 25, which had high mean scores of 2.62, 3.45, 3.21, and 3.26 with standard deviations of .94, 2.32, .52, and .56 respectively. The cluster mean and standard deviation were 2.99 and .62 respectively. All the items under advancement were motivational factors except item 25 with a mean and standard deviation of 2.42 and .88 respectively which was not a motivator. In the respondents' opinion, principals had acquired further education and training since becoming principals and had acquired management experience on their job. It was also revealed that there was the possibility of self-actualization and opportunity for promotion. However, lack of support for professional growth was not motivating to the Principals. The cluster mean and standard deviation indicated that 'advancement' was seen as a motivator for principals' performance in the management of secondary education in South-South Nigeria.

Research Question 3: What are the principals' mean performance scores of principals in instructional supervision, in the management of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria?

The results of data analysis relating to the research question were presented in tables 13

Table 13: Mean ratings of teachers' responses on the extent of principals' performance in instructional supervision

S/N	Questionnaire items (instructional supervision)	\bar{X}	SD	DEC
My Principal				
1	inspects teachers' notes of the lesson to see if they are properly written	2.77	.97	F
2	examines students notebooks during class visits	2.43	.93	O
3	conducts unscheduled informal visits to classrooms	2.71	.89	F
4	points out specific strengths and weaknesses in teacher's instructional practices	2.57	.88	F
5	assigns teachers to classes according to their qualifications	3.00	.95	F
Cluster		2.69	.63	F

F= Frequently, O=Occasionally, DEC= Decision

From the data in table 13, the mean responses on principals' performance in instructional supervision in secondary schools in South-South Nigeria, ranged from 2.43 to 3.00. Items 1, 3, 4, and 5 had high mean scores of 2.77, 2.71, 2.57, and 3.00 with standard deviations of .97, .89, .88, and .95 respectively; while item 2 had a low mean score of 2.43 with a standard deviation of .93. The cluster mean and standard deviation are 2.69 and .63 respectively.

Based on the data, the respondents shared the view that principals frequently assigned teachers to classes according to their qualifications, inspected teachers' notes of the lesson to see if they are properly written, conducted unscheduled informal visits to classrooms, and pointed out specific strengths and weaknesses in teacher's instructional practices. However, the Principals' occasionally examined student's notebooks during class visits. The cluster mean and standard deviation showed that Principals frequently supervised instruction in schools. This indicated that principals' performance in instructional supervision in secondary schools in South-South Nigeria was high.

Research Question 4: What are the correlation coefficients between demographic and personality variables and principals' performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria?

Table 14: Correlation Coefficients between principals' demographic and personality variables and performance in instructional supervision.(N = 310)

Variables			r ²	Percentage
Age	Pearson Correlation	-.009	0.000081	0.01
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.876		
Gender	Pearson Correlation	-.022	0.000484	0.05
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.705		
Educational Qualification	Pearson Correlation	-.019	0.000361	0.04
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.737		
Area of Specialty	Pearson Correlation	-.019	0.000361	0.04
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.746		
Experience as Principal	Pearson Correlation	-.016	0.000256	0.03
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.781		
Experience as VP	Pearson Correlation	-.073	0.005329	0.53
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.202		
Marital Status	Pearson Correlation	-.024	0.000576	0.06
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.679		
State	Pearson Correlation	.039	0.001521	0.15
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.489		
Location	Pearson Correlation	-.143*	0.0204	2.04
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.012		
Leadership Style	Pearson Correlation	.342**	0.1169	11.6
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.096	0.009216	0.92
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.091		

The correlation coefficients between location, leadership styles of principals and performance in supervision (-.143, and .342 respectively) were substantial, though that of location is negative. Therefore, principals whose schools were located in the urban areas were more effective in instructional supervision than principals in the rural areas. Location explained 2.04% of the variance in principals' performance in instructional supervision. Principals that exhibited a more open leadership style were more effective in instructional supervision than those that exhibit a less open leadership style. Leadership style accounts for 11.70% of the variance in principals' performance in instructional supervision. There was no substantial relationship between age (-.009), gender (-.022), educational qualification (-.019), area of speciality (.737), experience as Principal (-.016), experience as Vice-Principal (-.073), marital status (-.024), state of origin (.039), motivation (.096) and principals performance in instructional supervision.

Hypothesis (H₀₁).

Demographic and personality variables do not significantly relate with principals' performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria.

Table 15: Analysis of Variance of Regression on Instructional Supervision

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	120.996	11	11.00	5.277	.000
Residual	621.120	298	2.084		
Total	742.116	309			

Predictors: (Constant), Age, Gender, Educational Qualification, Area of Specialty, Years of experience as Principal, Years of experience as Vice Principal, Marital Status, State, Location, Leadership style, and Motivation.

Table 15 showed that the F-value of 5.277 is significant at 0.000. This indicated that the demographic and personality variables of principals were significantly related to principals' performance in instructional supervision. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant linear relationship between demographic and personality variables and principals' performance in instructional supervision was rejected.

Table 16: Model Summary for Instructional Supervision

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error of the Estimate
	.404 ^a	.163	.132	1.44371

The coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.163. This indicates that 16.3% of the variance in instructional supervision is caused by variations in the predictor variables. Therefore, 16.3% of the variance in instructional supervision is predicted by demographic and personality variables.

Table 16: t-Values of the Demographic and Personality Variables on instructional supervision

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	6.176	2.333		2.647	.009
Age	-.002	.027	-.005	-.086	.932
Gender	-.215	.182	-.065	-1.178	.240
Educational Qualification	.001	.180	.000	.003	.997
Area of Specialty	-.058	.215	-.015	-.269	.788
Experience as Principal	-.007	.261	-.024	-.414	.679
Experience as VP	-.028	.017	-.084	-.481	.140
Marital Status	-.058	.261	-.057	-1.016	.310
State	-.002	.050	.059	1.066	.287
Location	-.507	.173	-.164	-2.924	.004**
Leadership Style	.173	.027	.347	6.441	.000**
Motivation	.019	.011	.093	1.699	.090*

(** Sig. at $P < 0.05$; * Sig. at $P < 0.1$)

To determine which of the variables were significantly related to or predicted principals' performance in instructional supervision, the t-values of each variable were presented in table 16. The t-values were age (-.086, $P < 0.932$), Gender (-1.178, $P < 0.240$), Academic qualification (0.003, $P < 0.997$), Area of specialty (-.269, $P < 0.788$), Experience as principal (-.414, $P < 0.679$), Experience as Vice-principal (-1.481, $P < 0.140$), Marital status (-1.016, $P < 0.310$), State of origin (1.066, $P < 0.287$), Location (-2.924, $P < 0.004$), leadership style (6.441, $P < 0.000$) and motivation (1.699, $P < 0.090$). Out of the variables, only location and leadership style had significant relationship ($P < 0.05$) with and predicted principals' performance in instructional supervision. Principals whose schools were located in the rural areas were less effective in instructional supervision than their counterparts in the urban areas. Principals who exhibited open leadership style were more effective in instructional supervision than those who exhibited close leadership style. The relationship between motivation of principals and their performance in instructional supervision tended towards significance ($P < 0.09$).

Discussion of Findings

Demographic variables of principals of secondary schools.

The results on demographic variables (age, gender, and educational qualification, area of speciality, experience as principal, and experience as Vice-principal, marital status, state, and location) of principals in secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria, showed that most of the principals are within the age bracket of 51-55 years. This means that most of the principals were

young. The government of South-South would have been guided by the proposition of Reyes (1990), and Feldman (1996) that young principals in their fifties exhibited better management capabilities than older principals since individuals tend to gradually disengage from active work with age.

Most principals in the secondary schools were males. Saduwa (2011) pointed out that although gender has its advantages and disadvantages for management effectiveness, the capability of the principal was more important. Most of the principals had served for not more than 11 years in that capacity. Besides, before most of the principals were appointed they have served as Vice principals for between six and ten years. The findings of the study showed that most of the principals were appointed from those who had served as vice principals. The situation where teachers who served as vice-principals were appointed as principals would enable the principals to be effective having understudied a principal in course of their professional growth. This was in line with the assertion of Lazear (2000), who noted that the Peter Principle in management theory recommended the selection of persons for superior positions based on their abilities relevant to the intended position.

Most of the principals in the secondary schools had first degrees rather than higher degrees. Besides, most of the principals had their qualifications in education-related areas other than specializing in educational administration and planning or non-educational areas. This is in line with different policy presumptions that teachers and principals should be professionally qualified. Eyike (2001) asserted that specialized training empowers and motivates principals for better performance. Ellah (2004) noted that professionally qualified principals tend to succeed more than their non-qualified counterparts in a situation where many things have to be managed. Therefore, professionally trained principals would perform their roles better than non-professionals in the management of schools.

It was also found that most of the principals were married. Anyanwu (2009) noted that the traditional virtue of marriage such as love, fidelity and mutual fulfilment imbibed by married men and women are presumed to transcend to the workplace where they exhibit love, mutual respect, and maturity that enable them to handle some complex problems. Thompson (2000) also noted that the performance of the principals would be influenced by their marital status since the emotional stability that comes with marriage is important in instructional leadership.

Personality (Leadership styles and Motivation) profile of principals of secondary schools

The results showed that principals in South-South, Nigeria exhibited open leadership style in the management of their schools. This is based on the fact that the principals communicated openly to staff about school activities, encouraging self-expression, creativity and interaction in the school, showed a feeling of concern and respect for staff and delegated duties to staff. The principals also involved teachers in decision-making, made appeals rather than command staff, were concerned about staff feelings, as well as showed concern for school goals and staff welfare. Therefore, it was clear that the principals exhibited more of open leadership style rather than a close leadership style of imposing tasks and duties on teachers, wanting things done their way, being resistant to change and being indifferent about activities in the school.

These findings agreed with the views of Udeh (2000) that the people-oriented style or open leadership style has democratic tendencies and demonstrates respect for every person in the group. It is characterized by adequate welfare attention, shared responsibilities, and group member's involvement in decision making, which encourages individual and group initiatives and creativity. Adeyemi (2010) noted that the democratic leadership of principals of secondary schools includes open communication, shared decision-making, a delegation of duties, support and trust, working with teams, and empathy, improved human relations, corporation, and teaching and learning. Okorie (2010) also observed that principals leadership behaviours that serve as

antidotes of motivation of teachers to higher performance are: empathy, a delegation of duties, oral commendation, recognition through presentation of gift items and involvement in decision making.

The findings of this study showed that factors such as nature of work itself, recognition, responsibility, achievement and advancement are sources of motivation for principals in the management of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria. The results showed that the nature of the work principles does serve as a motivator. This is based on the fact that what they did is meaningful, interesting, and required their initiatives in carrying their duties effectively.

Therefore, the factors that motivated principals in the management of secondary schools were nature of work, recognition, responsibility, achievement and advancement. Okolo, Haruna, and Oguche (2013) observed that motivation plays a vital role in the job satisfaction of teachers and they perform better when given challenging work, the opportunity for growth, recognized, and provided with their basic needs. The authors explained that motivated staff exhibits more commitment at their workplace. According to Ejike (2011), intrinsic motivating factors like nature of work, recognition, responsibility, achievement and advancement would spur workers to high performance. These motivational factors are important to principals' performance and need to be sustained in the management of secondary schools in South-South, Nigeria since the main aim of motivating staff is to get the best out of them. It is assumed that motivated staff will exhibit commitment at the workplace. There is the need to encourage principals by adequately motivating them, to get from them the highest level of commitment desired as the administrative heads of secondary schools. Sinden and Hoy (2008) noted that the principal who is the chief executive officer of a secondary school needs to be well motivated towards the achievement of educational goals. This is because intrinsically motivated employees will perform better and therefore be more productive while remaining loyal to their employers and feel no pressure or need to move to a different firm. Kolawale and Fashina (2004) found that the motivation variables such as responsibility, a need for personal growth, recognition, achievement and work itself were significant in the job performance of the principals.

The extent of principals' Performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools

The findings of the study showed that principals' performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools was high. This was on the basis that the principals frequently assigned teachers to classes according to their qualifications, inspected teachers notes of lessons to see if they were properly written in line with the content of the scheme of work, conducted unscheduled informal visits to classrooms, pointed out specific strengths and weaknesses in teacher's instructional practices, and occasionally examined students notebooks during class visits. These findings agreed with that of Agbo (2013) those principals perform different instructional supervision roles. Chika and Ebeke (2007) observed that, among many factors that influence learning and achievement in secondary schools, principals' instructional management seem to be the most intervening factor. Haruna (2008) also noted that instructional supervision is the most important responsibility of a school principal in the management of secondary schools since all efforts in all educational settings are geared towards promoting effective teaching and learning. The school administrators' ability to effectively see that aspects of instructional delivery in the school system are properly carried out is a responsibility that must be given high premium. Students' inability to excel in external examinations could be attributed to the uncovered scope of work in the syllabus during the teaching and learning process. Okwor (2001) observed that in a situation where the principal devotes little or no time to instructional responsibilities, the quality of education offered to the students cannot be effectively and adequately ascertained and guaranteed. Enyi (2012) underscored the need for principals to ensure effective supervision of

teachers' lesson plans before delivery to see if they are properly prepared to enhance teaching and learning.

Therefore, Supervision of instruction is one of the indispensable and paramount tasks of an effective administrator in the operation of a good school system. The Principal must see that meaningful learning is taking place in all the classes and that the teachers are teaching what they are supposed to teach, and in a manner that the students understand and enjoy their lessons.

Demographic and personality variables as correlates of principals' performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools

The findings showed that there was a substantial relationship between some demographic and personality variables and principals performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools. Location and leadership styles related to principals performance in instructional supervision.

Location-related with principals' performance in instructional supervision. Principals whose schools were located in urban areas were more effective in instructional supervision than their counterparts in rural areas. This could be attributed to principal's sensitivity to their school's proximity to government agencies that supervise schools. Ikediugwu (1999) in a study found that location was a strong factor in secondary school administration.

There was a correlation between the leadership style of the principals and performance in instructional supervision. Principals that exhibited a more open leadership style were more effective in instructional supervision than those that exhibit a less open leadership style. Okorie (2010) noted that leadership is an essential factor that propels the management of all internal and external aspects of an organisation and attributes largely to the achievement of goals. The leader exerts much influence on how people interact, communicate and conduct the activities of the organisation through motivation and delegation of duties. Oyewole and Alonge (2013) noted that the moral decadence and other social vices in our school system today can only be changed through principals' leadership role in instructional supervision. The authors are of the view that principals affect this change by assisting teachers in determining the right methods, teaching facilities, physical settings, classroom attributes that are most likely to promote effective learning in schools. Similarly, the findings of the study corroborated with that of Shaman (2006) on a study on the attributes of school principals leadership style and capacities for secondary schools. The results showed a strong positive correlation between the perception of teachers on principals' leadership styles and effectiveness in their duties since effective leadership removes rift among members in the school and promote cooperation for the achievement of intended goals through teaching.

Demographic and personality variables as predictors of principals' performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools

The findings of this study showed that the demographic and personality variables (age, gender, educational qualification, experience, marital status, location, state motivation and leadership style) jointly had a significant relationship with principals' performance in instructional supervision. The findings further showed a significant relationship between some demographic and personality variables with principals performance instructional supervision. For instance, the location of the school had a significant relationship with principals' performance in instructional supervision; there was a significant relationship between leadership style and principals' performance in instructional supervision.

These findings agreed with that of Okpe (2010), on the influence of demographic variables and school climate on principals' job performance in public secondary schools in South-East, Nigeria. The results showed that educational qualification, experience, and gender jointly and significantly influence principals' job performance. Specifically, schools administered by married principals

with higher qualifications had the best results. The results of the study did not agree with that of Ibukun (2011) and Ogunsanya (2001) that there was a significant difference between principals' age and their administrative effectiveness. These findings disagreed with that of Onyiri (2007) on principals' attributes and administrative effectiveness of public and private secondary schools. The results show that there was no significant difference in the influence of principals' age, experience, qualification, and forthrightness on the administrative effectiveness of private and public schools. Their performances only differ due to close supervision of instruction which was higher in private schools.

The findings of the study also showed that Location had a significant relationship with principals' performance in instructional supervision. These findings agreed with that of Akiri and Ugborugbo (2008) that the performance of teachers was significantly influenced by location. Teachers in urban areas performed better than those in semi-urban and rural areas. The results of their study further revealed that the performance of female teachers was significantly influenced by location. Female teachers performed best in urban schools and worst in rural schools.

The findings of this study revealed that leadership style had a significant relationship with principals' performance in instructional supervision. Principals that exhibited a more open leadership style were more effective than those that exhibited close leadership styles in instructional supervision. Most effective administrators were those that exhibited openness by helping guide their teachers in instructional delivery. These are features of democratic behaviour which support all social activities and give strength to the feelings of personal dignity and self-expression, creativity, group interaction and effective performance. The findings of the study agreed with that of Oyewole and along (2013) which showed a significant positive relationship between principals' instructional supervision roles of principals and the motivation of teachers in the discharge of their duties.

These findings agreed with those of earlier studies. Nwaeze (2003) reported that leadership styles had a significant relationship with organizational climate. Effective leadership exerts positive relationships, and the ability to deal with complex issues and manage change. Kolawole and Fashina (2009) also reported that there was a significant relationship between principals leadership style and job performance. Studies by Jack (2012), and Duze (2012) reported that there was a significant relationship between principals' leadership style and secondary school teacher's job satisfaction. Secondary school teachers agreed that only democratic leadership exerts a positive influence on their job satisfaction. A study by Napodia (2010), Nwankwo, Loyce and Obiorah (2011) showed that leadership styles are significantly related to principals administrative effectiveness.

However, these findings were contrary to earlier studies. For instance, Adegbesan (2013) showed that there was no significant relationship between the principal's leadership style and teaching/learning atmosphere. Sawati, Anwar, and Majoka (2011) also reported that there is no significant influence of any particular management style of high school administrators and schools' academic results.

The findings of this study revealed that motivation only tended towards significance with principals performance in instructional supervision. The findings agreed with that of Akanbi (2003) that the relationship existing between intrinsic motivation and employee performance was insignificant. The findings also agreed with that of Okolo, Haruna, and Oguche (2013) that there was no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female secondary school teachers on the extent to which motivation influences teachers' job performance. However, these findings were contrary to earlier studies. For instance, Aba dulahi (2010) and Ekere (2010) reported that motivation had significant relationship with employees' performance

Conclusion

The principals in South-South, Nigeria are mostly males, young, married who have first degrees, and have served as vice principals before their appointment. Therefore, principals are appointed from the stock of vice principals. Leadership style and school location predicted principals' performance in instructional supervision. Principals exhibited open leadership styles which were handy in improving their performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools. Principals' performance was high in instructional supervision. This task area is the usual concern of the principals in their day to day management of their schools.

Educational implications

The findings of the study revealed that leadership style had a significant and positive relationship with principals' performance in instructional supervision.. The leadership behaviours exhibited by the principals from the findings of the study such as accessibility; communicating openly to staff about school activities; encouraging teachers self-expression, creativity and interaction; showed concern and respect for staff; and delegating duties to them enhanced teachers' co-corporation, and commitment to duty impacted positively on performance in instructional delivery.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and the various implications which have been highlighted, the following recommendations were made:

1. The appointment of principals should not be based on age and gender since they had no significant relationship with principals' performance in instructional supervision in the management of secondary schools.
2. Training and re-training programmes should be given to principals to help them adopt more open leadership styles to pay adequate attention to an instructional supervisory role.
3. Although motivated, effort to improve the level of motivation of principals should be made by the government through the Ministry of Education on the provision and maintenance of school facilities to enhance their performance since they represent government and implement the programmes in the schools in instructional supervision.

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